

Dictating Impact of Systemic (Trans)formations on Management Re-engineering in R&D Firms

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Abstract : This paper examines challenges to the implementation and internalization of benchmarked management practices by research organizations in developing economies as transformative tools towards commercialization. The purpose is to understand the contributing influence of internal organizational factors from both situational and historical perspectives towards the practice implementation constraints, and also to provide theoretical understanding on how systemic formations and transformations in the organizations' activities influenced the level to which their desired needs are attained. The results showed that the variability in the outcomes of the organizations' transformation processes was indicative of their (in)ability to deal with the impacts of cumulated tensions in the systemic interfaces of their organizational activity systems. It is concluded that the functionalities of the systemic interfaces influence the functionality of the organizational activity system.

Keywords : Organizational activity system; practice implementation; systemic formations; systemic transformations; management re-engineering; R&D firms

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